

Synthetic MRI aids in glioblastoma survival prediction

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Synopsis:

Radiomics systems for survival prediction in glioblastoma multiforme could enhance patient management, personalizing its treatment and obtaining better outcomes. However, these systems are data-demanding multimodality images. Thus, synthetic MRI could improve radiomics systems by retrospectively completing databases or replacing artifacted images. In this work we analyze the replacement of an acquired modality by a synthesized counterversion for predicting survival with an independent radiomic system. Results prove that a model fed with the synthesized modality achieves similar performance compared to using the acquired modality, and better performance than using a corrupted modality or a model trained from scratch without this modality.

Main Findings:

- Synthetic MRI can contribute to glioblastoma survival prediction within a radiomics-based approach.
- Replacing an actual acquired modality by a synthesized counterversion in the inputs of an independent radiomics system achieves similar performance in survival prediction accuracy.

Purpose: Survival prediction in glioblastoma multiforme prognosis is a key task for treatment and surgery planning. Radiomics is a frequently used technique in the oncology field for quantitative decision making when images are involved. Synthetic MRI is progressively gaining popularity and its applications for data harmonization¹ or data augmentation^{2,3} for segmentation or classification algorithms are well-known. Synthetic MRI, in addition, allows the practitioners to reduce acquisition time, to retrospectively complete databases or to replace artifacted images. In this abstract we pursue the application of synthetic MRI to improve a radiomics approach for survival prediction in glioblastoma. To the best of our knowledge, only one MRI-related work⁴ uses synthesized modalities as input to a radiogenomic system. However, in this work image synthesis and the radiomics pipeline itself are intimately coupled since classifiers are trained with synthetic data. Therefore, it is inherently impossible to quantify the benefits of synthetic imaging. Furthermore, the authors solely use geometrical features, for which the precision in the intensity values of the synthesized modality is not a critical issue. Thus, in this work we thoroughly analyze the replacement of an actual acquired modality by a synthesized counterversion for predicting survival with a completely independent radiomic system. Our results allow us to state that Synthetic MRI does add up to glioblastoma survival prediction within a radiomics-based approach.

Methods:

Acquisitions and preprocessing: Four different datasets of glioblastoma patients were used in this work (see Table 1). All the acquisitions were performed with IRB approval and informed written consent. For each patient, four image modalities — T1-weighted (T1w), T2-weighted (T2w), T2w FLAIR, and T1w post-contrast (T1w-c) — were co-registered to 1mm³ and skull-stripped following BraTS preprocessing in CaPTk⁵. Then, two pipelines are followed; on the one side, denoising⁶ and N4 bias correction⁷ were performed to segment white matter and tumors^{8,9}. On the other side, N4 bias correction was applied on the skull-stripped images and these were normalized dividing each by the mean intensity of the white matter region contralateral to the tumor.

Synthesis: We synthesized a FLAIR image modality from a T1w and a T2w following the synthetic MRI approach of Ref¹⁰. *Dataset24* (see Table 1) was used to train the self-supervised CNN¹⁰ in a leave-one-out scheme (i.e., a total of 24 models were trained). For training each model, one patient is used for testing and the remaining patients are randomly split between training (~80%) and validation (~20%).

Radiomics: *BraTS*, *TCIA*, and *Dataset22* (174 patients in total, see Table 1) are used to train the radiomic system. Starting from a total of 138.267 handcrafted features extracted from all modalities available in each patient, we trained the radiomic system following a nested cross-validation scheme (outer=5-fold; inner=10-fold). The classifier model was trained in each inner split (IS), while the feature selection methods^{11,12} were repeated in each outer split (OS) to reduce the possible bias produced if training were done on a single cross-validation split. We randomly split the dataset between training and validation (139/35 patients) for each OS. The training data of each OS is further divided between training and validation (125/14 patients) for each IS. For each OS, the model with the lowest Brier loss in the IS is chosen. Note that five models were selected for the following screening. Each of these models are then tested with the validation data corresponding to its OS. The model with the best performance, measured with the area under the curve (AUC), is selected. The resulting model of this process was an extreme gradient boosting with 16 features, three of which belong to the FLAIR modality.

Experiments: We carried out four test experiments with *Dataset24*. In all of them, the acquired T1w, T2w, and T1w-c were used as inputs to the system; but in each of them the FLAIR modality varies between a) acquired, b) synthesized, c) corrupted, and d) the radiomic system was trained from scratch without this modality. Note that the synthesized FLAIR images used were the test images from the leave-one-out scheme. The AUC, F1-score and linear regression were computed to compare the experiments.

A flowchart of the aforementioned process is shown in Figure 1.

Results: Figure 2 shows a representative slice of the synthesized FLAIR images for several test glioblastoma patients. Figure 3 shows the AUC and the F1-score for the different experiments. Finally, Figure 4 shows scatter plots of the output probabilities and labeled predictions from the acquired FLAIR versus the other experiment configurations.

Discussion: Our results show that synthesized FLAIR images are visually similar to the acquired images in both healthy and unhealthy regions. The performance achieved with their usage in the radiomic system is not only close to the performance achieved using the acquired image, but also substantially better than using both a corrupted image and a model trained without this modality. This is also confirmed with the R^2 values. Experiments on a larger cohort would be advisable to further support our conclusions.

Conclusion:

We assessed the performance of a radiomic system when an input acquired modality was replaced with a synthesized version. Results prove the utility of using synthesized modalities to feed a radiomic system for survival prediction of glioblastoma patients.

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Figure 1: Radiomics flowchart. Preprocessing: after the CaPTk⁵ pipeline, two pipelines are followed; the first one is aimed at obtaining high quality segmentations, and the second one performs the intensity normalization. Feature extraction and selection: features are extracted and a combination of feature selection methods (*TuRF*¹¹ and *mRMR*¹²) are used. Different classification methods are tested to obtain a final model. Extreme gradient boosting and Random Forest are selected for a model with and without the FLAIR, respectively. Finally, four experiments are carried out.

Figure 2 (460/500 characters): A representative axial slice of the synthesized and the corresponding acquired FLAIR images for different test patients. a) Synthesized images by the self-supervised CNN¹⁰. b) Corresponding acquired images. The synthesized images are close to the acquired versions regarding the structural information and contrast between tissues in both healthy and pathological regions. Particularly, the contour and intensity of the different lesion areas are similar in both. Note that in patient two the synthesized FLAIR does not suffer from motion artifacts.

Figure 3: Area under the curve (AUC) and F1-score of the radiomic system tested with *Dataset24* when the FLAIR input modality is the a) acquired, b) synthesized, c) corrupted, and d) when a radiomic system trained from scratch without this modality is used instead. Both metrics are substantially better in case b) than in the cases c) and d). The comparison between a) and b) shows that the performance of the system is equal in terms of AUC, and only suffers from a slight degradation in terms of F1-score.

Figure 4: Scatter plots of the probabilities and labeled predictions obtained as output of the radiomic system for the experiment with the acquired FLAIR versus a) synthesized, b) corrupted, and c) without the FLAIR modality. Dashed lines represent the threshold fixed in the radiomic system to classify survival (>480 days). Each point represents each glioblastoma patient and its color corresponds to the ground-truth labels. R^2 values from the linear regressions are provided. Note the good agreement of points in a) compared to b-c).

Table 1: Datasets used in this work. *BraTS* and *TCIA* are public datasets, whereas *Dataset22* and *Dataset24* are private datasets of two institutions. Survival is defined as the time in days from diagnosis to death (censored=0) or the last date that the patient was known to be alive (censored=1). All sessions are composed of four modalities, namely, a T1-weighted (T1w), a T2-weighted (T2w), a FLAIR, and a post-contrast T1w (T1w-c). Details about the scanner and the sequence are provided if available.

Dataset	n	Age (SD)	Survival (IQR)	Censored	Survival < 16 months	Scanner	T1w TE/TR (ms)	T2w TE/TR (ms)	FLAIR TE/TR/TI (ms)	T1w-c TE/TR (ms)
<i>BraTS</i>	119	62±12	374 (364)	0	65.6 %	19 institutions	NA	NA	NA	NA
<i>TCIA</i>	33	60±10	518 (390)	3 %	60.1 %	8 institution	352 -3379 / 2.75 -19	700 - 6370 / 15 - 120	6000 - 11000 / 34.6 - 155	4.9 - 3285/ 2.1 - 20
<i>Dataset22</i>	22	65±10	451 (307)	22.7 %	59.1 %	1.5T GE and 1.5T Philips	7.61 / 740	102 / 5260	127 / 8000 / 2000	2.56/7.96
<i>Dataset24</i>	24	57±13	552 (218)	29.2 %	54.2 %	1.5T GE	1.83 / 5.98	122 / 4162	142 / 9350/ 2200	2.18 / 6.85
Whole dataset	198	61±12	468 (360)	7 %	62.6 %					